

Evaluation of multiple-choice and short essay questions in pharmacology education

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Abstract: Multiple choice questions (MCQs) and short essay questions (SEQs) are common methods of the assessment of medical students in courses of pharmacology. Poorly constructed test items (questions) are widespread problem resulting in failing to assess learning objectives. It has been reported that there are 36.0% to 65.0% flawed test item in medical education assessment tool. Thus, the objective of this study was to evaluate MCQs by determining the item writing flaws (IWFs) and to evaluate the SEQs by determining the cognitive level of each item. Four pharmacology tests were administered to third year pharmacy students at Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Omar Al-Mukhtar University, Bayda, Libya. These were evaluated by determining the IWFs and the level of the cognitive domains. Based on the Buckwalter's modification of the Bloom's taxonomy cognitive level, for the SEQs, 30.0% of the questions were attempted to check recall of information, 26.0% were attempted to evaluate understanding and interpretation of data and 43.0% of the questions were attempted to check the application of knowledge for solving a particular problem. For the MCQs, 94.6% of the questions were attempted to evaluate understanding and interpretation of data. For the IWFs, there were more than 40.0% flawed questions. The most common writing flaws were the negative stem (47.4%), unfocused item (16.0%), non-homogenous in grammar and in contents (10.0%), all the above (10.0%) and clang association (05.0%). In short essay, the SEQs were in excellent quality because they were equally distributed between the three levels of cognitive (level I, II and III). On the other hand, the most common mistakes IWFs of the MCQs were the negative stem (47.0%) and the idea was not clearly and concisely stated in the stem (16.0%). This study concludes that questions in SEQs are valid to measure the learning objective but MCQs were not in pharmacology courses in Libya.

Introduction

The main objectives of any educational program are to enable learners to develop different cognitive abilities, such as recalling the fundamental or the principles (lower cognitive order) or the problem solving or the clinical reasoning. To ensure that the

learners acquired the intended performance or competency, evaluation or assessment must be conducted and aligned with the learning objective, during or at the end of the education program. In pharmacology education, assessment(s) is overly

critical tool that evaluate the learners' knowledge, skills and attitude consequently learners' outcomes or educational quality. Different type of assessment demands more emphasis on certain construct (category) for example objective structured clinical examination (OSCE) use standardize patients to evaluate counselling, clinical procedure, application and clinical problem solving. The OSCE, for instance in Pharmacy School, must be passed by examine to be a practice pharmacist. On the other hand, MCQs and SEQs are used to assess basic knowledge and clinical reasoning based on learning objectives resulting either in passing or failing in educational course [1]. In any assessment, two elements: cognitive level and item writing principles are essential in governing the quality and validity of the assessment.

Bloom specifies cognitive abilities into knowledge (facts, basic and principles), comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Most educational programs such as medical and pharmacy practice attempt to develop the medical curriculum (both instruction and assessment) that incorporates not only base information (basic and principles) but also complex cognitive abilities [2]. Thus, quality crafted assessment should reflect the basic and the more complex skills. Students are evaluated based on these cognitive abilities [2]. According to the revised Bloom's taxonomy, most of the learning objectives and the examination questions were classified under the lower level of cognitive domains [3]. Despite the important of the complex cognitive skills, most educational program measure just the recall or the basic or fundamental information [2]. Measuring just basic knowledge results in learners with poor learning outcomes. Recently, modified Bloom's cognitive levels categorize the cognitive levels into: level I (recall of information), level II (understanding and application) and level III (problem solving). In addition, for writing MCQs guideline, there was no recognized guideline for writing well-constructed MCQs. Nevertheless, Haladyna and Downing [4] developed guideline for writing well-constructed MCQs. Following the standard items of writing principles results on well-crafted questions. However, failing or violating the guidelines or

principles of writing MCQs results high frequency of flawed items in the tests studied (item writing flaws, IWFs) [5], pausing challenge to learners. Further, flawed items in MCQs lead to incorrectly classifying students as failed when they should have classified as passed. MCQs consist of stem (posing question), 3 - 5 alternative options: one correct answer (key) and distractors (2 - 4 wrong answers). With ease of scoring, higher reliability and validity, MCQs is commonly used either alone or in combination to measure the basic knowledge or synthesis, application and problem solving skills [6] as described by the learning objectives. On the other hand, essay type assessment is the time consuming but can be used alone or in combination to measure the ability of learners to recall facts and to apply or solve problems [6]. One of the most common problems of MCQs is the IWFs, i.e., unfocused stem or implausible distractors. Also, the deficiency of the SEQs is the focus on the low order of cognitive domain, such as ability to recall facts. Flaw items or low order cognitive questions fail to assess learning objectives [6]. In short, the SEQs may emphasize in one level of the modified Bloom's cognitive levels while the MCQs may have flawed questions such as negatively worded items or unfocused items. Thus, the purpose of this study was to evaluate MCQs and SEQs items in undergraduate students of Pharmacology course by determining IWFs in MCQs and cognitive levels of each item in MCQs and SEQs in Libya.

Materials and methods

This analytical study was conducted at Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Omar Al-Mukhtar University, Bayda, Libya. The study was conducted between the academic years (2020 and 2022). All the examinations were performed by qualifying lecturers of pharmacology with experience in teaching for more than five years. Different methods of assessments such as MCQs and SEQs were used as module of assessments. The Department developed all the assessment questions in multiple choice or in short essay questions. Four pharmacology examinations involving MCQs and SEQs according to **Tables 1** and **2**. Each question in the MCQs was analysed to evaluate for IWFs

(Table 2). In addition, MCQs and SEQs were analysed to evaluate the cognitive level (Table 1). The cognitive levels of the assessment tools were analyzed using the modification of the Bloom's taxonomy [7]: Level I includes questions which attempt to check recall of information. Level II includes questions which attempt to evaluate understanding and interpretation of the data. Level III includes questions which attempt to evaluate the application of knowledge for solving a particular

problem (Table 1). For determining types of IWFs standard criteria given by previous studies [4, 5, 8] were used and commonly occurring violations of item-writing guidelines were identified (Table 2). Although there were no humans involved in the descriptive study, we mean the study was assessing the validity of the pharmacology examinations. An ethical consent was obtained from the Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Omar Al-Mukhtar University, to evaluate the examinations.

Table 1: Modified Bloom's taxonomy

Level I	Knowledge	Recall of information
Level II	Comprehension and application	Understanding and interpretation of data
Level III	Problem solving	Use of knowledge and understanding in new circumstances

Table 2: Judging the MCQs according to the presence of IWFs

Type of IWFs	Idea is not clearly and concisely stated in the stem (unfocused)
	Negative stem
	Clue to the right answer (clang association)
	Not homogenous in grammar or in content structure
	Using all above
	Using none of the above

Data analysis: This is a quantitative study and a descriptive statistic has been used to analysis the percentage of the cognitive level in MCQs and in SEQs, and the percentage of flawed items in the four tests. Based on Haladyna and Downing that have developed guidelines for writing quality crafted questions [9], therefore, a predict can be obtained if MCQs or SEQs are well constructed and can measure the learning outcomes.

Results

In this study, the examinations are designed to assess lower cognitive skills such as recall of information and higher cognitive abilities such as problem-solving quality. Items in the MCQs or in the SEQs are designed to test the student ability to recall, understand, to apply what the students have learned. To assess students' academic successes, these assessments should not have any IWFs and the questions should be evenly distributed between

the different cognitive levels. To verify if the items in MCQs or SEQs, assess the student's ability in lower and upper cognitive skills and free of any IWFs, four pharmacology examinations were selected and analyzed for the level of cognitive ability and the occurrence of writing flaws. For the IWFs flaws, (Figures 1 and 2) of the one hundred questions, there were more than 40.0% flawed questions. *What are most common writing flaws?* The most common writing flaws were the negative stem (45.0%), unfocused item (15.0%), non-homogenous in grammar and in contents (10.0%), all the above (10.0%), clang association (05.0%) and none of the above (05.0%). For the level of cognitive ability, in SEQs, Figure 3, the questions were scattered testing the recall of information (25.0%), application (20.0%) and problem solving (40.0%). Nevertheless, in MCQs, Figure 3, only 03.0% of the question were evaluating the recall of information, 02.0% were evaluating the problem

solving while many of the questions (94.6%) were testing the understanding and interpretation. In short, in SEQs, there was a scattered distribution of

the cognitive levels while in MCQs, most of the MCQs were intended at the understanding and interpretation of the data (94.6%).

Figure 1: Percentage of IWFs in four tests of Pharmacology course

Figure 2: Percentage of flawed items in four tests of Pharmacology course

Figure 3: Percentage of different cognitive levels in four pharmacology tests
 Where C1, C2 and C3 are represent the cognitive level I, II and III, respectively.

Discussion

Assessment is the essential part in learning process. It usually spreads to cover the lower cognitive abilities such as assess learners to recall factual knowledge or assess higher cognitive skills for instance learner's ability to analyse, apply or solve the problems [6]. In addition, occurrence of writing flaws or uneven distribution of the cognitive levels in writing the test reduces the test validity or quality in assessing the learners' academic achievements. This study found that almost half of the flawed questions in four different pharmacology tests in Libya. The poorly crafted test items are common problems resulting on wasting of time, resources and money [10]. In medical education, 36.0% - 65.0% of test items were flawed and due to flawed MCQs, 10.0% - 15.0% of the students who failed should have passed [6]. As a result, the flawed tests are not valid to measure the students learning [9]. Also, the most type of the writing flaws were the negative stems (45.0%), unfocused stem (15.0%), non-harmonized grammar (10.0%), all of the above (10.0%) and none of the above (05.0%). Data of the current study positively correlate to the previous study in which found that most MCQs flaws are negatively-worded stems, unfocused-item stems, use of the all of above and none of the above [6].

The multiple assessment formats, MCQs and SEQs, used not only to assess the lower order cognitive skills (level I): recall of facts but also to assess the higher cognitive abilities (level II): understanding and application (level III) and problem solving [6, 11]. In MCQs, the current study shows that only 03.0% of the question item assessed recalling of facts, 02.0% of the questions assessed problem solving and 94.6% of questions assessed the understanding and application. On the other hand, in SEQs, 30.0% of the questions were in the level I (recall of facts), 26.0% were in the understanding and application (level II) and 43.0% were in the problem solving (level III). Present findings indicated that questions in MCQs and SEQs, using Bloom's taxonomy cognitive levels were unevenly distributed between cognitive levels. It is a potential that the questions measure

the entire span of Bloom's cognitive level. The current study also showed that greater proportion of SEQs (30.0%) than MCQs (03.0%) were testing lower level of cognitive skills. Similarly, greater SEQs (26.0% level II and 43.0% level III) than MCQs were evaluating the higher cognitive skills. However, SEQs were evenly distributed between cognitive levels. On correlation with the literature, Palmer et al. [11] showed that greater proportion of questions testing lower level of cognitive skills. This means that the assessment (i.e., MCQs) did not cover the spectrum of Bloom's cognitive level resulting in inferior quality or validity assessment. The present study showed that greater proportion of SEQs (30.0%) were testing lower level of cognitive skills. In line with the literature, Palmer et al. [11] showed that more proportion of questions testing lower level of cognitive skills, what does this mean? This intended that the assessment (i.e., MCQs) did not cover the spectrum of Bloom's cognitive level resulting in inferior quality or validity assessment. Further, it is a trend to find most of the questions focus on testing low order thinking skills such as what are the side effects of propranolol?, Or which of following medications used for pregnancy hypertension?. This type of questions assess students on recalling or remembering facts, they are easy to design. On contrast, it is not common to find questions which assess the higher order thinking skills, for instance, compare the effects of high-dose (1000 mg/d) and low dose (100 mg/d) aspirin on a long-term cardiovascular patients?.

Conclusion: This study indicates that questions in SEQs are evenly distributed between cognitive levels while in MCQs, the questions are unevenly distributed in Libyan medical universities. Also, the assessment have 50.0% flawed item and most item writing flaws are negatively worded stem, unfocused stem, non-homogeneous in grammar, using all the above and none of the above. Thus, it can be concluded that SEQs are valid to measure the learning objective but MCQs are not in Libyan medical universities.

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